

Effects of Human-Swarm Interaction on Subjective Time Perception: Swarm Size and Speed

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ABSTRACT

Many large-scale multi-robot systems require human input during operation in different applications. To still minimize the human effort, interaction is intermittent or restricted to a subset of robots. Despite this reduced demand for human interaction, the mental load and stress can be challenging for the human operator. A specific effect of human-swarm interaction may be a hypothesized change of subjective time perception in the human operator. In a series of simple human-swarm interaction experiments with robot swarms of up to 15 physical robots, we study whether human operators have altered time perception due to the number of controlled robots or robot speeds. Using data gathered by questionnaires, we found that increased swarm size shrinks perceived time and decreased robot speeds expand the perceived time. We introduce the concept of subjective time perception to human-swarm interaction. Future research will enable swarm systems to autonomously modulate subjective timing to ease the job of human operators.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → **Collaborative interaction.**

KEYWORDS

Swarm robotics; Human-Swarm Interaction; Time perception; Flow

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1 INTRODUCTION

Swarm robotics as an embodiment application of swarm intelligence has significantly gained scientific interest during the last two decades [18, 29]. Many studies in swarm robotics have demonstrated great potential in transferring simplified laboratory- and simulation-based research into real-world applications. Examples can be found in domains like precision farming [2], environmental monitoring [58], industry 4.0 [42], and firefighting [51]. Many research questions remain and include the human factor of interaction with robot swarms, namely Human-Swarm Interaction (HSI) [38], a sub-field of Human-Robot Interaction (HRI).

A swarm of robots is self-organized without central control and is often designed as a fully autonomous system. However, semi-autonomous approaches remain relevant in many real-world applications where the human role shifts from an operator with full control to a supervisor or collaborator, who only guide the swarm toward a desired goal. This collaborative approach requires rethinking traditional affordances for control mechanisms and increases interest in bidirectional interaction and communication methods [31]. Designing self-organized robots for interaction with humans requires cognitive robots with the ability to understand the effects of their actions not only on their physical environment but also the mental state of their collaborator [6]. Further research suggests a low-level integration between the robot swarm and the human nervous system toward a "joint human-swarm loop" [30]. Within the EU-funded research project, *ChronoPilot* [9], we envision a future of robot swarms that are aware of their psychological impact on humans with whom they are collaborating and enabling the robots to adapt their behavior accordingly. First, we need to understand these effects before we can find ways of quantifying them and using them as feedback in adaptive behavior.

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There are many studies on the effects of robots on emotion [60]. The role of emotion is not only investigated in the context of single-robot interaction but also for robot swarm characteristics. For example, Dietz et al. [17], found effects of robot motion on the user's emotional response in regard to the robots' speed in a swarm, and also their smoothness and synchronization. Similarly, Podevijn et al. [53] found effects of increasing robot numbers on the psychophysiological state of their human participants, including their emotional response.

However, the aspect of time perception has been largely neglected in human-robot interactive systems [47]. Time is one of the fundamental dimensions of our existence. It is of high importance for our cognition and many of our actions rely on a subjective percept of time passing [28]. We know the feeling of time flying by, or dragging. Our subjective time perception is created within the brain and decoupled from physical time. It is continuously modulated by stimuli, experience, state, and context. This malleability can be used to obtain active influence on someone's time perception. Basic research in psychology has isolated and quantified different influences based, for example, on cognitive load [36], emotion [20] but also motion [11]. These effects could be found in the interaction between humans and robots as a result of the robots' actions and behavior. Hence, we interpret robot behavior in human-robot interaction as a complex time perception modulator that is essential to be understood. Especially, in the specific case of HSI, we expect an amplified effect of the robots' behavior due to the large number and limited control. We argue, that to establish a symbiotic relationship between a human operator and a robot swarm, the robots require a cognitive ability to account for their influence on the time perception of their interactive human collaborators. Our proposed approach toward this goal is to investigate individual variables in the context of HSI as a foundation for future research in time perception-aware robots.

In the presented study, we investigate the time perception-related psychological effects with different swarm sizes and robot velocities in an active interaction scenario. Past and ongoing research in psychology on subjective time perception and the modulation of time perception, as well as time perception in robotics, is exemplified in Sec. 2 to provide a starting point for our investigation. The presented results support our theory of robot behavior as a time perception modulator and give suggestions on the types of effects we can expect to see. However, our aspired experiments on human-robot interaction come with significantly increased complexity that seems out of reach for a controllable psychological experiment. We hypothesize that both variables have a significant impact on the cognitive load of the operator and, thus, affect time perception-related factors, mentioned above. In a series of experiments with humans interacting with a swarm of up to $N = 15$ physical robots, we have investigated this hypothesis intending to show significant changes in human time perception. We present related work, our experimental method, and our results to form a basis for future research on adaptive and time perception-aware robot (swarm) behavior.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 Time perception

Subjective time perception refers to the mental representation of time within our brain. Neurologically, it is not completely agreed upon how this is created. Different models suggest dedicated temporal mechanisms, while others rely on intrinsic dynamics being responsible [33]. Either way, time is a fundamental aspect of how we experience the world and it is strongly linked to our emotional and cognitive state [66]. Research on this topic is conducted across many different disciplines including, for example, computational and robotic modeling [3]. Therefore, it is important to work with a common conceptual framework and coherent terminology [62]. In this study, we have selected two categories of subjective time perception that are of interest: duration judgments and passage of time judgments. The former describes the estimation or production of an interval, while the latter refers to how fast the passage of time is perceived. Both are concerned with how time is perceived subjectively, it has, however, been shown that there is no direct link between the two [21].

How we perceive time is affected by temporal and non-temporal variables in different types of stimuli [1]. Studies to date provide evidence supporting the modulatory effect of space and quantity on time judgments, with more of space or quantity being mostly equal with more time (e.g., [12, 49, 65, 68]). Perceived time can be lengthened by increases in velocity of motion [11, 35, 63], intensity [14, 23, 26, 41], weight [44], quantity, size, luminance, and numerosity [19, 61, 68], as well as by apparently larger visual stimuli [55], thus pointing to a critical interplay between temporal and nontemporal magnitude information. The interference of magnitude information in duration judgments is evident for intervals in both the subsecond [13, 43] and the suprasedond range [54, 68], yet the effects of nontemporal information on time judgments highly depend on the attentional resources allocated to the nontemporal stimulus containing the magnitude information [68]. That is, the effect of quantity, size, and numerosity is evident only when attending to the stimulus presented, but manipulations in luminance levels interfere with temporal judgments irrespective of the attention allocated to the stimulus, probably because luminance differences can be easily perceived without explicitly attending to the stimulus [68].

Cognitive load as a measure of used cognitive resources, often also applied as a reference for task difficulty, provides a less clear but noteworthy effect on time perception. In psychology, contradicting results on the effects of cognitive load on time perception concerning the evaluation paradigm were found. An extensive meta-analysis showed that statistically, duration judgments increase with increasing cognitive load under the *retrospective paradigm* (i.e., participants were unaware of the later time judgment asked), while the opposite effect can be observed under the *prospective paradigm* (i.e., participants were aware that a time judgment will be asked of them) [8]. Here, we decided to work with the prospective paradigm, as not informing the participants limits the possible experiments to one per person.

Cognitive load and task difficulty are important aspects in human-centered engineering research. As a result, it represents a bridge between different disciplines, including psychology, concerning the

effects on time perception. As an example, also in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) [7] this topic combination can be found. In their study, Block and Gellersen [7] show an experiment where perceived time, measured based on subjective performance, is reduced with increasing cognitive load. Their suggestion is to use this aspect to improve user experience and task performance.

Experimental research in psychology on these stimuli is usually done in controlled environments on isolated variables in the second or millisecond range. Here, we follow the novel approach of combining different stimuli in a more complex real-life scenario in the minute range. We hypothesize that the effects of motion, the number of stimulus elements, and the cognitive load of the task are major factors in the suggested scenario. Individually, they have experimentally been shown to affect time perception. The advantage of this approach is that we can try to study time perception in a robot setup. The disadvantage is that even if we find correlations, we cannot prove definite causation due to the experiment depending on multiple variables.

2.2 Time perception in robotics

Interest in the psychological effects of robots on humans dates back to at least 1997 [34, 59]. However, with a growing desire toward close collaboration between humans and robots, research has significantly expanded recently. Within, a new research direction on artificial cognition to adequately consider the temporal dimension has been formed [45]. The capacity to perceive time is considered fundamental for conscious artificial intelligence [46]. Cominelli et al. [15] recently presented a preliminary model of their artificial cognitive architecture for social robots, called SEAI (Social Emotional Artificial Intelligence), to which they added a time perception dimension. The argument is this would allow the robots to understand human time perception. They suggest continuing with an experimental evaluation of this model in a social robot.

Until now, time perception remains a niche topic in HRI. One example shows a study in which a robot bases its timing to ask a human for help on the human's subjective duration estimation as a task [37]. Their results showed that appropriate timing concerning the subjective estimation increases the acceptance of the robot as a partner.

Other examples focus more on the concept of perceived flow, which is commonly linked with a distorted time perception [32]. More precisely, flow is considered as a state of optimal cognitive load in between boredom and anxiety, which is a balance between personal skill and task demand [16]. As an example, Marti et al. [48] suggest that flow in HRI is caused less by specific attributes of a robot and instead through stimulating interactions. Their study considers a qualitative exploration of three different robot types for their effects on time perception and flow during interaction [48].

Multi-robot systems and swarms add further dimensions and complexity that could affect time perception and flow, such as robot-robot interactions and a perceived swarm magnitude. At the time of this study, no literature discussing the specific effects of multi-robot or swarm systems on subjective time perception could be found. However, timing aspects have been shown to affect the performance of human-swarm systems, a concept called *neglect benevolence* [64]. In their study of a foraging scenario, Walker et al. [64] discovered

Figure 1: Experiment scenario

Figure 2: Arena with robot start positions (red → 1 robot, red & orange → 5 robots, all → 15 robots).

that giving a swarm time to stabilize their emerging behavior after issuing a command and before issuing the next command, could improve the task performance. Adaptive robot behavior to interact with the user's time perception could in this case be leveraged to facilitate optimal timing strategies. Inspired by the intrinsic time domain of emerging behavior and the variety of possible stimuli due to the number of distributed agents, this study is focused on the effects of robot swarms on time perception.

3 METHOD

3.1 Scenario

To evaluate how swarm size N and robot speed v affect subjective time perception, we designed a six-round experiment with an active robot interaction task. We test three different swarm sizes of $N \in \{1, 5, 15\}$ robots, as well as two different robot speeds of $v_{\text{slow}} = 0.04 \frac{m}{s}$ and $v_{\text{fast}} = 0.2 \frac{m}{s}$. As this is the first study done on timing and swarms, we selected the parameters based on the upper limits of feasible robot speeds and spatial constraints of the lab in terms of swarm size to initially study the full range of possible scenarios. Throughout the experiment, the participants were sitting on a chair in our lab next to a 2.2 m \times 1.6 m robot arena marked on the ground with black tape as shown in Fig. 1. The robots operated in a semi-autonomous way. In each cycle, by default, they followed a simple behavior as described in Sec. 3.3.2.

As an external control input for the robots, the participants were given a single push-button mounted on an 8cm \times 8cm 3D printed cube. At the beginning of each round, the robots were placed in

Table 1: Experiment outline, two blocks (A and B) with three rounds each, each round consisting of three tasks given in Table 2.

Round	Block	# Robots	Robot speed	Duration
1	A	$N = 1$	v_A	~6 min
2	A	$N = 5$	v_A	~6 min
3	A	$N = 15$	v_A	~6 min
4	B	$N = 1$	v_B	~6 min
5	B	$N = 5$	v_B	~6 min
6	B	$N = 15$	v_B	~6 min

fixed starting positions inside the arena as shown in Fig. 2. After starting the task, the robots began moving around in a random pattern. The participants were told to keep all robots inside the arena by using the control button. Once pressed, the button triggers all robots to rotate on the spot in a random direction until the button is released (for more detail see Sec. 3.3.2).

3.2 Experiment procedure

Before beginning the experiment, all participants were given a brief introduction to the research project and the overall procedure. They were further asked to read the upcoming questionnaires to remove a possible bias in the first round. Consequently, our time perception values were collected under the *prospective paradigm* given that the participants were informed about their task before the start of the experiment.

An overview of the experiment outline and the experimental conditions is shown in Table 1. Each experiment round has a variable duration that sums up to about six minutes because it consists of several tasks as described below. The experiment is separated into two blocks of three rounds each, beginning with $N = 1$, then $N = 5$, and finally $N = 15$ robots. Half of the participants were exposed to the slow speed $v_A = v_{\text{slow}} = 0.04 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ for the first block and fast speed $v_B = v_{\text{fast}} = 0.2 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ for the second block, while it was the opposite for the other half ($v_A = v_{\text{fast}}$ and $v_B = v_{\text{slow}}$).

We did not randomize the swarm size, instead, we increase task difficulty and therefore cognitive load with each round, to allow participants to get used to the task. This, means that we accept learning and habituation, but at the same time, we expect difficulty differences to rather out rule any potential effect of such confounds.

Each experiment round consists of three individual tasks as shown in Table 2. First, the participants were asked to rest for two minutes, while watching a relaxing aquatic video [52] to establish a baseline in the physiological measures captured during the experiment. Note that no physiological data are presented in this paper. Then followed the main task, where participants interacted with the robots for three minutes. In the end, the participants were asked to fill in a short approximately one-minute questionnaire about their experience during the robot interaction task. As a result, each round took approximately six minutes to complete. With a total of six rounds per participant, preliminary consent, demographic questionnaire, preparation, and introduction to the experiment, the total duration for each participant was approximately 45 minutes.

Table 2: Experiment round consisting of three tasks.

Task	Duration
Baseline/Rest	2 minutes
Robot Interaction	3 minutes
Questionnaire	~1 minute

Ethical approval for this study was granted by the ethics commission at the University of Lübeck¹ and following the declaration of Helsinki [67].

3.3 Robot Swarm

3.3.1 Hardware. We used the Thymio II robot [56], equipped with a Raspberry Pi for enhanced control and connectivity, and an auxiliary battery pack as shown in Fig. 3. The robot uses a differential drive system for locomotion with a maximum linear velocity of $0.2 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ and has a footprint of around $11 \text{ cm} \times 11 \text{ cm}$. The Thymio II robot has nine infrared sensors with two pointing to the ground, two to the rear, and five to the front. We used the five front-facing infrared sensors for obstacle avoidance. However, due to their limited range of approximately 10 cm the latency of changes in motion was insufficient to completely avoid collisions at fast speed v_{fast} . All robots were labeled with an ArUco² marker for position tracking with a ceiling-mounted camera during all experiments. An example of the collected trajectory data can be seen in Fig. 4.

Figure 3: Modified Thymio II robot used in this experiment.

3.3.2 Behavior. The robots were programmed in Python using the library *thymiodirect*³ to perform a random walk with obstacle avoidance and allow for user interruption. A robot goes straight with a fixed speed $v \in \{v_{\text{slow}}, v_{\text{fast}}\}$ for a random time, sampled from a uniform distribution between 1 and 10 seconds. Once this time has elapsed or if an obstacle is detected, the robot rotates on the spot in a random direction by inverting the speed of one of its wheels for a random time sampled from a uniform distribution between 0.5 and 3 seconds. After the rotation, the robot returns to a state of straight motion and samples a new random time. The participants can interrupt this process by pressing a button, which triggers a message being sent to all robots over the communication

¹reference number: 22-042

²https://docs.opencv.org/4.x/d5/dae/tutorial_aruco_detection.html

³<https://github.com/epfl-mobots/thymio-python>

Figure 4: Example for robot paths showing all conditions recorded during the experiment from one participant.

protocol ZeroMQ⁴. While the button is pressed all robots rotate on the spot in a random direction by inverting the speed of one of their wheels. This way we grant the participants limited control over the robot trajectories to keep the robots inside of the arena. A three second timeout was implemented to limit the duration of the button being pressed and prevent continuous pressing while waiting for the experiment to end as a strategy. However, the timeout was reset upon release of the button or timeout, the robots sample a new time and return to straight motion. For an example of the robot paths, see Fig. 4.

3.4 Self-reported measures

For each experiment, we recorded several pseudonymized measures with informed consent from the participants. Before beginning the experiment, we asked the participants to fill in a questionnaire collecting demographic information on their age group, gender, educational background, and their experience with robots.

After each experiment round, we asked the participants to fill in a questionnaire consisting of six items in three different categories. The first category focused on time perception with an item on duration judgments and an item on passage of time judgments. For the duration judgments, the participants were asked to estimate the duration of the robot interaction task and to indicate a time on a visual timeline between 1 and 5 minutes with an indicator every 30 seconds. For the passage of time judgments, we utilized a 5-point item of Likert type asking the participants to indicate how they experienced time passing ranging from very slow to very fast. The second category was used to capture the participant’s self-reported affective state with the help of two items on valence and arousal from the Self-Assessment-Manikin questionnaire [10] on an item of 9-point Likert type. Lastly, we included two items on the self-rated experience of flow, asking the participants to rate their experience of flow on an item of 9-point Likert type between ‘not at all’ and ‘very much’, and the perceived task requirement on an item of 5-point Likert type from ‘too low’ to ‘too high’.

⁴<https://zeromq.org>

3.5 Participants

For the experiment, we recruited participants through the university e-mail distribution list to all students and employees. The selected criterion was that all participants had to be older than 18. We offered no financial compensation for this study.

A total of 25 people with an age group distribution of 40% between the ages 18 to 20, 56% between the ages 21 to 29, and 4% between the ages 31 and 39. 12% of our participants had an academic background in robotics with a further 32% in computer science or related fields, and 52% in natural sciences including psychology. Furthermore, the demographic questionnaire revealed an almost even distribution between females (44%) and males (52%) with an additional 4% of diverse participants.

4 RESULTS

We statistically analyzed the self-reported measures of time perception, duration estimation, flow, and perceived difficulty. The raw rating data from the self-reported measures were analyzed using the SPSS 25 software (SPSS inc.). Greenhouse-Geisser correction [27] was applied whenever the sphericity assumption was violated. To estimate participants’ consistency, we first calculated Cronbach’s α per task across the number of robots and robot speed. Standardized Cronbach’s α results revealed acceptable to excellent consistency [25] between participants’ ratings in each task ($\alpha = .99, .93, .73, .95$ for difficulty, flow, duration estimation, and passage of time, respectively).

4.1 Perceived difficulty

A 2×3 repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to test the effect of robot speed ($v_{\text{slow}}, v_{\text{fast}}$) and the number of robots ($N \in \{1, 5, 15\}$) on perceived task difficulty (see Fig. 5). The perceived difficulty was generally higher with more robots and the faster robot speed, but for the $N = 1$ condition, speed effects were very small. We observed a significant main effect of robot speed and the number of robots, as well as a significant interaction: $F(1, 24) = 59.93, \eta p^2 = .71, F(2, 48) = 149.53, \eta p^2 = .86, F(2, 48) = 14.83, \eta p^2 = .38$, all $p < .01$. Post-hoc comparisons

(Bonferroni-corrected, $\alpha = 5\%$) showed that the $N = 15$ condition ($M = 3.48, SE = .13$) was perceived to be significantly more difficult than the $N = 5$ ($M = 2.40, SE = .13$) and $N = 1$ ($M = 1.18, SE = .08$) conditions. Similarly, the $N = 5$ condition was more difficult than the $N = 1$ condition. Post-hoc analyses on the interaction showed that the fast-slow difference in experienced difficulty was significantly smaller for the $N = 1$ condition as compared to both the $N = 5$ and $N = 15$ conditions, whereas it did not differ for $N = 5$ and $N = 15$ conditions.

Figure 5: Mean perceived difficulty as a function of number of robots for both speed conditions. Error bars show confidence intervals. Connecting lines to guide the eye.

4.2 Flow

To test the influence of robot speed v and swarm size N on the flow judgments another two-way ANOVA was done (see Fig. 6). Flow increased with more robots and faster robot speed but both effects vanished with higher numbers of robots. The main effects of robot speed, number of robots, as well as their interaction were statistically significant: $F(1, 24) = 15.48, \eta p^2 = .39, F(2, 48) = 27.03, \eta p^2 = .53, F(2, 48) = 4.83, \eta p^2 = .17$, sequentially (all $p < .01$). Follow-up Bonferroni post-hocs indicated higher flow for the $N = 15$ ($M = 6.08, SE = .26$) and $N = 5$ ($M = 5.82, SE = .30$) than $N = 1$ ($M = 4.18, SE = .33$) condition. However, the $N = 15$ condition was not significantly higher in flow than the $N = 5$. Bonferroni-corrected post-hoc t-tests that followed up on the interaction tested whether the fast-slow differences in flow differed between the number of robot conditions. Fast-slow differences were significantly larger for the $N = 1$ as compared to the $N = 15$ condition, whereas the $N = 5$ condition did not significantly differ from the other two in this respect.

4.3 Duration estimation

A 2 (robot speed v) \times 3 (swarm size N) repeated measures ANOVA on estimated duration (see Fig. 7) yielded a significant main effect of swarm size $N, F(2, 48) = 10.65, p < .01, \eta p^2 = .31$. However, neither the main effect of robot speed nor the interaction between robot speed and number of robots reached significance, $F(1, 24) = .06, p = .81, \eta p^2 = .00, F(1.45, 34.88) = .42, p = .60, \eta p^2 = .02$, respectively. Next, Bonferroni corrected tests revealed that duration was estimated to be longer for the $N = 1$ ($M = 2.58, SE = .11$)

Figure 6: Mean perceived flow as a function of number of robots for both speed conditions. Error bars show confidence intervals. Connecting lines to guide the eye.

condition as compared to the $N = 5$ ($M = 2.30, SE = .11$) and $N = 15$ ($M = 2.07, SE = .12$) conditions. Further, although the estimated duration for the $N = 5$ condition was numerically longer than with $N = 15$ robots, this comparison did not reach significance.

Figure 7: Mean duration estimation as a function of number of robots for both speed conditions. Error bars show confidence intervals. Connecting lines to guide the eye.

4.4 Passage of Time

Another 2×3 within-subjects ANOVA tested the effect of robot speed v and the swarm size N on the passage of time judgments (see Fig. 8). Time passed faster for the participants with a higher number of robots and faster robot speed. The analysis revealed a significant main effect of robot speed, $F(1, 24) = 19.60, \eta p^2 = .45$ and number of robots, $F(2, 48) = 44.86, \eta p^2 = .65$, both $p < .01$; the interaction between number of robots and robot speed was not statistically significant, $F(1.57, 37.71) = 2.40, p = .12, \eta p^2 = .09$.

5 DISCUSSION

In a novel experiment, we evaluated the impact of robot speed and swarm size on the time perception of a human operator in an active human-swarm interaction task. We recorded a data set that includes self-reported measures of 25 participants with six

Figure 8: Mean perceived passage of time as a function of number of robots for both speed conditions. Error bars show confidence intervals. Connecting lines to guide the eye.

different test conditions each. Beyond self-reported measures, we also collected qualitative data while conducting the experiment. It is based on short, unstructured interviews with the participants, and informal observations from the study which were recorded as notes for reference. Recurring and interesting points were noted during discussions among the authors which are worth mentioning.

Using the statistical analysis of the self-reported measures, we can draw several conclusions between our preliminary hypothesis and the outcome. Here, we investigated the effects of swarm size and robot velocity on human time perception, task difficulty, and flow. In short, we found that swarm size influences all tested measures, while the robot velocity shows no effect on duration estimation and partially limited effects on the other measures. Next, we discuss the results in more detail.

As expected, faster speeds and a higher number of robots increased the perceived task difficulty excluding the $N = 1$ robot condition (see Fig. 5). Taking the perceived task difficulty as a metric of cognitive load, we can see a decrease in prospective duration judgment with increasing task difficulty in our results. While we cannot identify cognitive load as the dominant time perception modulator, we can speculate that cognitive load was a relevant variable here. This is supported by other studies, where cognitive load showed similar effects on prospective duration judgment [8]. The lack of speed effects for the $N = 1$ robot condition could be because at no moment many control inputs were required from the participants and the focus remained on one robot only. In the $N = 5$ and $N = 15$ robot conditions, the attention had to be shared between more agents increasing the effect of the speed variable.

The participants' flow rating gives statistically significant results on the main effect of both variables and their interaction. The post-hoc analyses on the interaction showed the strongest speed effects in the $N = 1$ robot condition, whereas it converges toward the $N = 15$ robot condition between the fast and slow conditions. For the fast condition, we notice the trend of a decrease in perceived flow between $N = 5$ and $N = 15$ robots. $N = 5$ fast robots numerically resulted in the highest perceived mean flow rating. We can speculate that the task of controlling $N = 5$ robots is located between boredom and stress. Following this idea, the condition of $N = 15$ fast robots

exceeded a 'comfort zone' of cognitive load for most participants toward a feeling of stress or anxiety.

This interpretation is supported by recurring findings in our qualitative data. More than half of the participants verbalized that they felt a loss of control during the experiment round with $N = 15$ fast robots and asked if anyone had accomplished keeping all robots inside the arena under this condition. The $N = 1$ robot condition shows the largest difference between slow and fast robots for perceived flow, but the smallest for perceived task difficulty. Although both conditions were perceived as easy, a slow robot might have caused boredom, while a fast robot might be cognitively appealing.

A supporting observation for this assumption can be taken from Fig. 4. We can see in the example plots on the right for the $N = 15$ slow and fast robot condition that the robots are mostly kept close to the arena boundary instead of traversing across, highlighting the difficulty to control them. In contrast, several participants mentioned that they barely had to intervene during the condition with $N = 1$ slow robot causing boredom, whereas $N = 1$ fast robot can be controlled and also completely traverses across the arena.

For our main objective of modulating time perception through robot speed and swarm size, we see statistically significant effects in both measures of duration estimation and passage of time perception. For duration estimation, we have significance for swarm size between $N = 1$ and $N = 5$ only. Increasing swarm size to $N = 15$ shows a shorter estimation as a trend. The speed variable did not show any effect on duration estimation. Interestingly, only $\sim 11\%$ of all recorded estimations were at or above the actual duration of three minutes. What could have caused such a tendency for underestimation is an open question. In the passage of time analysis, we get more significant effects compared to the duration estimation measure. Here, both variables of speed and number of robots show significant effects of an increased passage of time with an increasing number of robots and speed.

6 LIMITATIONS

Naturalistic settings pose a challenge to study time. As a result, the presented study and its results are subject to limitations based on design decisions and the nature of mutually interacting effects in complex scenarios. To expand the preceding discussion, provide insights into our experience, and highlight design considerations for follow-up studies, we present the main limitations.

Swarm size was not randomized, but increased during each speed condition from lower to higher numbers to increase the cognitive load in each round. This could have possibly induced ordering effects from learning, habituation, or mental fatigue, which could confound the findings. However, our results do not agree with the expected effects of learning and habituation, which would likely yield stretched time perception. While learning and habituation do not provide an alternative explanation for our findings, we can only limit the effects to the design of this study and further research with randomized swarm size order would be desirable to generalize the effects.

Mental fatigue in the later stages, in contrast, in principle could contribute to perceiving the task as more difficult and to perceiving time compression. However, the study took only 45 minutes,

a duration after that typically only very small fatigue effects are observed [24], and fatigued attention can be at least partly restored by high fascination environments like our robot environment [4]. Additionally, the participants received a two-minute break while watching a relaxing video between the different experiment rounds. Therefore, it seems unlikely that fatigue had a considerable contribution to the observed effects of swarm size, even if we cannot entirely exclude that possibility.

A number of studies showed that time perception is strongly linked to emotional experiences (e.g., [22, 40]). We, therefore, need to consider how far the observed effects of robot number and robot speed are direct effects of stimulus characteristics or mediated by variables like emotion or task difficulty. One may, for instance, speculate that higher task difficulty increases emotional arousal and, thus, contributes to changes in subjective time beyond direct stimulus effects. Furthermore, while conducting the study, we noted that the acoustic noise of the robots' motors vastly differed in all conditions. One slow robot was acoustically almost not noticeable, but 15 fast robots produced a screaming sound. This effect can be heard in our supplemental video. These differences in robot sound might have influenced time perception via arousal or attention. However, neither sound nor task difficulty can fully explain our time perception results because the influences of robot number and speed on subjective time do not match well with those on sound or task difficulty. A deeper analysis of the psychological variables that might mediate the effects of stimulus characteristics on subjective time will be the subject of future studies with robot swarms.

The selected user input method only facilitates limited control over the robots and allows for a strategy in which the primary attention would not be on the robots by repeatedly pressing the button. As a result, the robots would mostly rotate on the spot instead of moving toward the boundary of the arena, limiting the effects of their speed and number on the participant. While we can only speculate about the different strategies applied by the participants, only two participants briefly showed this behavior, allowing us to neglect this limitation. Nevertheless, it could provide meaningful insights to introduce a performance metric as motivation or collect further information on the chosen strategy.

7 FUTURE WORK

The results from this experiment offer many great opportunities for additional studies in the future. We are currently working on a psychological analysis of the correlation between time perception and emotional response using self-reported measures of valence and arousal.

From the HSI perspective, the next step is to make time perception measurable for use in an adaptive system. To go beyond self-reported measures in HRI, often physiological measurements are used [5, 39]. A recent study has shown that it is possible to use cardiac data to predict subjective time perception [50]. In our experiment here, we measured the physiological responses with an Empatica E4⁵ wristband and a Polar H10⁶ ECG chest strap and used the Lab Streaming Layer (LSL)⁷ to record the data. We recorded the

following five features: electrodermal activity, blood volume pulse, skin temperature, wrist acceleration, and electrocardiogram.

Besides the physiological response, it was shown that salient changes in visual perception can be used to produce duration estimations matching human reports [57]. In our experiment, we recorded the robot positions via external tracking as shown in Fig. 4. We would argue that robot motion represents a major salience change in the participant's visual input. Hence, allowing for a similar study.

We plan to combine features derived from the physiological measurements and possibly the robot positions as contextual data. With a machine learning approach, we could then train a classifier for online prediction of subjective time perception. We plan to follow the work by Orladic et al. [50] and possibly extend it with artificial neural networks.

8 CONCLUSION

In summary, we find a coherent overall picture. For fast robot speeds, we see a threshold between $N = 5$ and $N = 15$ robots where the cognitive load exceeds an assumed ideal flow state. The effect is visible also in the perceived passage of time, but not in duration estimation. So we assume that there is a close relationship between the perceived passage of time and flow, while our ability to estimate duration is not strictly connected to our perception of flow. Instead, our results show an almost linear scaling of duration estimation over swarm size, which is similar to the perceived difficulty, except for $N = 1$ fast robots. Duration estimation and passage of time perception show effects in different directions. Durations that are perceived as passing fast are estimated as shorter than durations that are perceived as passing slow.

Overall, we can conclude that our ability to estimate duration is influenced by the number of robots we are interacting with, but not necessarily their speed. Our passage of time perception is affected by both variables and likely correlates with our perceived flow state. We believe that these findings can be exploited for HSI in a variety of applications. With the knowledge of how swarm size and robot speeds affect time perception, adaptive control approaches can be developed to actively modulate the human operator's time perception. This adaptive active time modulation could be programmed into the robots to react online to the user's needs. Modulating a person's duration estimation could, for example, be useful in time-critical scheduling tasks. Modulating the perceived passage of time and flow could be used to increase task performance and user satisfaction in an HSI scenario.

With this paper, we have introduced the concept of subjective time perception to human-swarm interaction. Out of our many findings, especially, the significant effect of swarm size on a human operator's time perception will motivate further research. A key breakthrough will be to enable a robot swarm to autonomously and possibly in a decentralized approach react online to the operator's current time perception to put the person in to flow state.

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⁵<https://www.empatica.com/en-int/research/e4/>

⁶<https://www.polar.com/de/sensors/h10-heart-rate-sensor>

⁷<https://labstreaminglayer.readthedocs.io>

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